

NFDI4Earth

Deliverable D1.2.1 & D1.2.2

Trend Scouting

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Executive summary

This document collects trends in digitization in the geosciences, including but not limited to automatic metadata extraction and annotation, semantic mapping and harmonization, machine learning, data fusion, visualization and interaction.

The objective of this collection is to steer the exploration of new potentially relevant building blocks to be included in NFDI4Earth and related NFDI consortia.

This is a living document with annual deliverables and it combines the deliverables D1.2.1 and D1.2.2. It is an initial structure, which can easily be adapted in the future, if the consortium decides for another structure for the documentation.

Contributions

Based on CRediT Contributor Roles, see <https://credit.niso.org/>.

SB: Writing – original draft

YF: Writing – original draft

MS: Writing – original draft

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1 Introduction

In the following sections, the updates in the reporting period will briefly be summarized. The state of this document is current on July 31st 2023.

In the current state this report documents an ongoing process: it contains a template for the description of a trend (with a few, elementary information chunks) in the last section, as well as four exemplary trends in sections 2 to 5.

2 Knowledge Graph (KG)

Author: Yu Feng **Updated last:** 2022-07-11

2.1 Abstract

A Knowledge Graph is a knowledge base that uses a graph-structured data model or topology to integrate data. It is a concept now extended to the geography domain, e.g., answering questions like: “What is here?”, “What happened here before?” to assist decision makers and data scientists to enrich their data with connected information.

Figure 1: The Linked Open Data Cloud

2.2 Application scenarios

- Disaster emergency response, e.g., associating the demographical data with the disaster observations for spatial search and query
- Precise farming, e.g., land potential analysis
- Annotating training data with environmental features, e.g., Symbolic Background Knowledge for Machine Learning (1st Cohort Incubator lead by Benjamin Risse).

2.3 Challenges

- Quantifying and representing regional differences
- Detection and mitigation of bias in Geo-KG

2.4 Extended reading

- Openly accessible software: KnowWhereGraph. <https://knowwheragraph.org/> (Accessed on 11.07.2022)
- "Know, KnowWhere, KnowWhereGraph: A densely connected, cross-domain knowledge graph and geo-enrichment service stack for applications in environmental (Janowicz et al. 2022)

3 Hierarchical Data Format (HDF)

Author: Yu Feng Updated last: 2022-08-25

3.1 Abstract

The Hierarchical Data Format is an open-source file format that supports large, complex, heterogeneous data ('Hierarchical Data Formats - What is HDF5?', n.d.). The current version is the Hierarchical Data Format version 5 (HDF5). The key advantages of HDF5 mainly include: (i) support for heterogeneous data (e.g., any n-dimensional datasets); (ii) portable and easy-to-share, with no vendor or platform lock-in; (iii) cross-platform, from laptops to massively parallel systems; (iv) fast I/O allows for access time and storage space optimizations; (v) keep metadata with data, streamlining big data lifecycles and pipelines(Li, n.d.) .

Figure 2: An example of HDF5 structure, that contains groups, datasets and associated metadata('Hierarchical Data Formats - What is HDF5?', n.d.).

3.2 Application scenarios

- Storage and processing large ESS related dataset (1st Cohort Incubator lead by Hao Li).
- Deep learning with faster data access

3.3 Challenges ('Moving Away from HDF5.', n.d.)

- Complex and low-level specification, long documentation
- Loss of data when corruption happens
- Few supported data types, e.g., tuples unsupported

3.4 Extended reading

- Documentation of HDF 5(Lütkebohle, n.d.)
- Python and HDF5: unlocking scientific data (Collette 2013)

4 Inter Planetary File System (IPFS)

Author: Yu Feng **Updated last:** 2022-08-25

4.1 Abstract

The Inter Planetary File System (IPFS) is a protocol, hypermedia and file sharing peer-to-peer network for storing and sharing data in a distributed file system. The current default way to exchange data across the Internet is HTTP, but it fails in some cases. Large files cannot be transferred using HTTP, data is not permanent on HTTP, HTTP mainly uses a Client-Server protocol which leads to low latency and makes it difficult to establish a peer-to-peer connection, also real-time media streaming is difficult on HTTP. All these failures are overcome using IPFS ('What Is IPFS?', n.d.). Unlike HTTP which is IP addressed, an IPFS network is content addressed. Which means, when any data is uploaded on an IPFS network, it returns a Hash and the data is then requested using that hash. Anyone can provide storage on the IPFS network and everyone is incentivized with crypto tokens. Data is distributed and replicated throughout the network which leads to data permanence. While requesting data it searches for the nearest copy of that data which leads to high latency and overcomes any bottleneck points. As the data is completely distributed, it has no scope for the centralization of data ('InterPlanetary File System.', n.d.).

Figure 3: An illustration of IPFS process ('What Is IPFS (Interplanetary FileSystem)?', n.d.)

4.2 Application scenarios

- Repository for field experiment data (Project EUREC4A - <https://eurec4a.eu/>)
- Storing climate model datasets on IPFS (1st Cohort Incubator lead by Marco Kulüke (Kulüke, Kindermann, and Kölling 2023)).

4.3 Challenges

- IPFS installation has a lot of hassles, it is not at all user friendly.
- IPFS consumes a lot of bandwidth which is not appreciated by metered internet users.
- IPFS currently is used by tech enthusiasts and normal people don't tend to set up their own node, which leads to the shortage of nodes on the network

4.4 Extended reading

- Documentation of IPFS. <https://docs.ipfs.tech/> (Accessed on 11.07.2022)

5 Transformers

Author: Steffen Busch **Updated last:** 2023-05-15

5.1 Abstract

Transformers use a self attention mechanism to adapt the features by combining the features of a complete sequence. First for each so called token of the input sequence (of length n) the attention layers generate 3 independent features, query (\mathbf{Q}), key (\mathbf{K}) and value (\mathbf{V}). Then attention aware feature (\mathbf{V}') is generated by calculating a weighted sum over all \mathbf{V} : $V'_i = \sum_j^n w_{ij} V_j$ for each token T_i , weighted by the similarity of Q_i to K_j , for example via the additive attention (Bahdanau, Cho, and Bengio 2016) or the dot-product. Thus even long range dependencies in sequential data could be captured due to the independence of the network structure from the sequence length n . While this attention mechanism could easily be integrated in decoders, encoders networks or even between them, the position information of a token gets lost and could be explicitly integrated by positional encoding, which adds position depending weights to each feature dimension. Figure 4 shows the structure of the first proposed transformer architecture (Ashish 2017). In the translation domain the input and output embedding could be, for example, a projected sentence and its possible translation. In both sentences the self-attention focusing independently on the important context and a third multi-head-attention block also pays attention to the correlation within the translation.

Figure 4: First transformer pattern by Ashish (2017). Source: (Amato, n.d.)

5.2 Application scenarios

- Natural language processing NLP
 - Translation
 - Text summarizing
 - Question answering
- Audio processing
- Computer vision

5.3 Challenges

- High demand for resources and data due to the dependence of the sequence length by the self-attention module.
- Exposure bias

5.4 Extended reading

- Attention is all you need (Ashish 2017)
- BERT: Transformers for Language Understanding (Devlin et al. 2018)
- Sequence to Sequence matching (Vinyals et al. 2015)
- A survey of transformers (Lin et al. 2022)

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- 'What Is IPFS (Interplanetary FileSystem)?' n.d. <https://medium.com/coinmonks/what-is-ipfs-interplanetary-file-system-7e48f32a7dce>.
- 'What Is IPFS?' n.d. <https://docs.ipfs.tech/concepts/what-is-ipfs/#decentralization>.

6 Template (Trend name)

Author: Name **Updated last:** YYYY-MM-DD

6.1 Abstract

[Caption (author, n.d.)]{.image}

6.2 Application scenarios

- first
- second

6.3 Challenges

- first
- second

6.4 Extended reading

- first
- second